

RESEARCH ON THE MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION OF DOLOMITE ROCK

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the initial data on the mineralogical study of dolomite rock, and is written to reveal the integral relationship of this rock with the cement binder in concrete, its effect on the strength of concrete, and all other properties.

Dolomite is a sedimentary carbonate rock consisting mainly of the mineral dolomite.

A group of carbonate rocks characterized by a high content of dolomite - dolomites, dolomitized or dolomitic limestones - are sometimes combined under the general name - dolomite rocks. The dolomite mineral was discovered at the end of the 18th century by the French mineralogist Dolomier and was named after him.

Dolomites are widely used both in their original form and after preliminary heat treatment.

After heat treatment, calcined at 800-900 °C, hydroxide dolomite finds application, in which CaCO₃ and MgCO₃ are in a highly active form, depending on the content of CaO and MgO. Often, the presence or predominance of one or another active oxide is necessary to obtain high-quality products. Thus, to obtain high-quality magnesium and dolomite binders and products based on them, the magnesium oxide composition contains essentially no or minimal calcium oxide.

Dolomite CaMg (CO₃)₂ is a double carbonate salt of calcium and magnesium. Dolomite differs slightly from limestone in its technical properties. The composition of pure dolomite includes: CaCO₃ - 54.2%; MgCO₃ - 45.8%. The composition of dolomite by oxides includes: CaO - 30.41%; MgO - 21.86%; CO₂ - 47.73%. Limestone with up to 10% MgCO₃ is traditionally called magnesia; limestone with a high content of MgCO₃ (up to 19%) is dolomitized.

Dolomite occurs in a coarse-grained or fine-grained compact form. The crystal structure of dolomite is hexagonal - rhombohedral. The color of dolomite is different: white, gray, light yellow, cloudy, almost transparent, brown - depending on impurities, iron impurities. Sometimes black dolomite is found, its color depends on the presence of bituminous or carbonaceous impurities in it. In the technique, the following are distinguished: granular

dolomite or dolomite marble, formed from grains of the mineral dolomite; dense dolomite, similar to dense limestone; calcareous dolomite, olitic or cellular dolomite.

Dolomite $\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$ contains impurities, namely magnesite, quartz SiO_2 , siderite, mineral groups of clays, FeO , Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , MnO and other organic substances. The specific gravity of dolomite $\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$ is from 2.85 to 2.95. Mineralogical hardness is 3.5-4.0; ultimate compressive strength is from 400 to 1300 kg / cm, heat capacity is 0.217 cal / g / deg.

The solubility of dolomite in water is less than that of calcite; however, in water saturated with carbon dioxide, its solubility increases greatly due to the formation of magnesium and calcium bicarbonates.

Formation of magnesium and calcium bicarbonates

In terms of solubility in mineral acids, dolomite occupies an intermediate position between calcite and magnesite. Dissolution in cold hydrochloric acid is slow; when heated, powdered dolomite dissolves completely in dilute hydrochloric acid, with the exception of insoluble impurities [17].

$\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$ dolomites are divided into two main genetic groups by origin:

- Exogenous;
- Endogenous.

The main mass of dolomites was formed in a monogenic form in marine conditions, and a disproportionately small number in continental ones. Endogenous dolomite formation is insignificant on the scale of dolomite formation.

In addition to these two main groups, there are also metamorphic dolomite rocks formed as a result of secondary alteration of monogenic sedimentary dolomites.

The main sources of calcium and magnesium in marine sediments are igneous and sedimentary rocks that formed the continents.

The weathering of these rocks resulted in soluble carbonate compounds of both elements, which were carried by surface waters into marine basins. Here, clastic material of various sizes was also transported during denudation.

The formation of marine dolomite was carried out by chemical precipitation, syngenetic and epigenetic methods; as a result of chemical precipitation and metasomatism during the diagenesis stage; due to clastic dolomite material; due to the vital activity of organisms.

Hemagentic dolomites, which have a crystalline structure, were formed as a result of direct precipitation of dolomite substances from seawater. Dolomite is saline in arid climates, deposited mainly in shallow water basins.

Diagenetic dolomites are formed as a result of the metasomatic interaction of freshly deposited lime mud and dissolved magnesia salts in water during the diagenetic period.

Detrital dolomites are formed as a result of the destruction and re-emplacement of completely or incompletely lithified dolomite sediments in shallow marine or coastal conditions, or as a result of the destruction of the coasts and seabed near the coasts formed by dolomites.

The formation of biogenic dolomites is associated with the vital activity of organisms in marine conditions.

Dolomites are widespread rocks. The main dolomite deposits in the Russian Federation are located in the Urals, Yakutia, Crimea, Buryatia, the Caucasus, the Far East and Siberia.

The main countries of dolomite deposits are: China, America, Canada, Mexico, Italy and Switzerland. They are also located in Central Asia, Ukraine, the Mediterranean, etc.

Uses of dolomite rocks: Dolomites are used in many sectors of the national economy in their natural and roasted state as an ore and technological raw material. The main consumers of dolomite are metallurgy, the industry of binders and thermal insulation materials, and construction. In addition, dolomites are used in a number of other industries and agriculture.

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